

Supplementary Information for

Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators to support management decisions for climate resilient forest ecosystems

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Survey: Internal consultation

There is need to condense the proposed 130 EFMI to a feasible number of indicators which can serve the needs in OptFor-EU (e.g. the explorer component in the DSS in WP4). In the project proposal we promised to do this in a **participatory process** with the CSA stakeholders. However, it was discussed that the sum of 130 indicators is way too high to be part of a survey to the forest managers in the CSAs. It was agreed that **we should first internally reduce the number of indicators by logical means** (e.g. all indicators for the DSS need to be sensitive to forest management). We can ourselves evaluate this. No need to bother the forest managers with this. Therefore, Stefanie suggested the following criteria for an “internal selection” of EFMI among the OptForEU partners:

- **Suitability** – Is the indicator suitable to assess the carbon mitigation potential?
- **Sensitivity to forest management** – Does the indicator allow to be influenced by active forest management?
- **Feasibility** – Does the indicator allow to gather precise data/information with reasonable time and financial resources?

Table S1: Overview of forest-related indicators structured along Classes of Ecosystem Services (ES), Forest Ecosystem Services (FES), associated issues, potential data sources as well as input for and output of the forest models (PICUS, 3D-CMCC-FEM), regional climate models (REMO, RegCM), land surface models (JULES) and the DSS as basis for a final set of Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators (EFMI).

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Supporting	Forest area as a basis of FES	Forest area	Forest area by forest types (ha, %)	Forest Europe 1.1 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg.	Increase	Monitoring changes in forest area is essential for assessing the impact of deforestation and forest restoration or afforestation efforts on forest-related carbon sequestration. Thus, an increase of the forest area increases the carbon mitigation potential by sequestration of carbon in woody biomass and forest soils and helps to achieve the greenhouse gas emission reduction commitments.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP FMP (UK) NFI, Management plans maps (RO). Land use shapefile; Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain)	Copernicus Pan-European Forest Cover dataset (see here), high resolution: 10-20 m, available for 2012, 2015, 2018 (basis of our EFT Map). Copernicus Global Land Cover dataset (see here) offers annual land cover maps at 100 m resolution, between 2015- 2019. ESA CCI Land Cover dataset (see here), annual data at a 300 m resolution between 1992-2020. Sentinel-2 Annual Land Use Land Cover (LULC) dataset (see here), high resolution: 10 m annual data between 2017- 2023 But this dataset does not offer PFT-specific information (i.e. only a single “tree” class), unlike the other datasets mentioned Land cover types: Trees, Water, Crops, Rangeland, Flooded vegetation, Built area, Bare ground, Snow/Ice EFT Map (task 1.4) PFT Map (task 1.4)	RS data as input for RegCM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Share of forest area in total land area (%)	SDG 15.1.1 Global Core Set 1 Forest Europe 1.1	Increase		FRA Forest Europe	Not relevant at local level Land use shapefile; Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain) Management plans maps, regional land use maps (RO)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Forest area annual net change rate (%)	Subindicator of SDG 15.2.1 Global Core Set 2	Decrease		INForest Database	Not relevant at local level FMP PNOA (Spain) Management plans maps, regional land use maps (RO)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Forest area available for wood supply (ha)	Forest Europe 1.1	Increase		FRA Forest Europe	FMP NFI (Spain) NFI, Forest management plans, statistics (RO)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Share of continuous cover forest area of total forest area (%) (Managed as continuous cover forestry)		Increase			FMP PNOA (Spain) NFI, Forest management plans, statistics (RO)	Continuous forests tend to have a greater potential to sequester carbon than forests with cleared spaces which are more prone to e.g. soil erosion. Thus, an increase of continuous forests increases the forest carbon mitigation potential.		See above “forest area”	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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		Expansion	Share of forest expansion by afforestation (%)	Part of Forest Europe 4.2	Increase	Forest expansion by afforestation (planting or seeding) of former non-forest area, leads to an increase of the forest carbon mitigation potential, as forest is next to wetlands the land use category with the highest carbon mitigation potential.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain) Regional land use maps, management plans statistics (RO)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Share of forest expansion by natural expansion (%)		Increase	Forest expansion by natural expansion on pastures, meadows, etc. leads to an increase of the forest carbon mitigation potential as in forest soils and biomass more carbon can be stored than in pastures or meadows.					<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Supporting	Primary production	Growing stock	Growing stock (m³/ha)	Forest Europe 1.2 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	When a forest's growing stock increases , its capacity to store carbon in the form of biomass also increases. This, in turn, allows the forest to mitigate more carbon emissions. However, as a forest matures and approaches its maximum carbon storage capacity, the rate of carbon sequestration may slow down.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP NFI (Spain) NFI (RO)	In Scandinavia, but also in other countries Laser scanning/Lidar is used to provide information on growing stock, see https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/12/8/1245 or https://cdns.cdnsciencepub.com/doi/10.1139/X09-042	PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data for simulated forest types	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Growing stock in forest available for wood supply (m³/ha)		Increase							<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Increment	Increment on total forest area (m³/ha)	Forest Europe 3.1 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	Increasing the increment increases the carbon sequestration in the living woody biomass and thus the carbon mitigation potential of the forest. However, we need to know the removals or heterotrophic respiration to know the net change of carbon sequestration.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP PNOA, NFI (Spain) NFI (RO)	FMP Regional Web Map Service; PNOA and NFI (Spain) NFI (RO)	PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Increment in forest available for wood supply (m³/ha)		Increase							<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Biomass stock	Above-ground biomass stock in forest (tons/ha)	Subindicator of SDG 15.2.1 Global Core Set 8	Increase	Greater biomass accumulation, both above- and below-ground, increases carbon storage, contributing to the mitigation of atmospheric CO ₂ levels.	INForest Database	FMP NFI (Spain) NFI (RO)	Sentinel-1/ASAR/ALOS ESA-CCI Biomass, 100 m resolution, annual data, 2010, 2017-2020 Global Forest review has a 30 m AGB product, but only modelled for the year 2000	PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs) JULES output (for point runs in CSAs), although not from all runs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Below-ground biomass stock in forest (tons/ha)		Increase							MITECO (Spain) NFI (RO)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Provisioning	Primary production	Wood products	Wood removals in forest available for wood supply (m³/ha)	Global Core Set 9 Forest Europe 3.1 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	tbd	The process of harvesting trees for wood products leads to a reduction in the amount of carbon that is stored in the forest. However, as long as the timber is not burned the carbon remains stored in long-lived wood products.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP NFI (RO)		PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
					Roundwood production (m³, m³/ha) -sawnwood -pulpwood		tbd		JFSQ	FMP Forest district statistics (RO)		PICUS output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fuel wood production (m³, m³/ha) -firewood -pellets, wood chips -wood charcoal					tbd	JFSQ	FMP Forest district statistics (RO)			PICUS output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

16 indicators

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Regulation & Maintenance	Carbon storage	Carbon sequestration	Carbon stock in forest biomass (tons/ha)	Forest Europe 1.4 EU Nature Restoration Law	Increase	Increasing carbon stocks in forest biomass (above- and below-ground), deadwood, forest soils, and in harvested wood products through sustainable forest management practices and logging contribute to climate change mitigation. Forest soil carbon levels are rather "static" in "mature" and continuous-cover forests. Or, it is at least, difficult to assess changes. Soil carbon levels are impacted by reforestation and/ afforestation activities and by different exploitation techniques.	FRA Forest Europe	NFI (data process); MITECO (Spain) Modelled NFI (RO)		JULES input data, although not for all runs JULES output (for point runs in CSAs), although not from all runs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Carbon stored in forest soils (tons/ha)	Forest Europe 1.4	Increase		Forest Europe ICP Forest soil survey	National forest soil inventories NFI (RO)	SMAP L4C data includes soil organic carbon estimates, which correlate well with model and forest inventory data (see Endsley et al., 2020) SMAP L4C provides daily global estimates of net ecosystem exchange, at a ~9 km, 3-hourly resolution	Validation RS data required JULES input data, although not for all runs JULES output data, although not from all runs PICUS, and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Carbon stored in deadwood (tons/ha)	Forest Europe 1.4	Increase		https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/09/decaying-forest-wood-carbon-climate-change-co2/	NFI (data process); MITECO (Spain) Modelled NFI (RO)		PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Carbon flux (MgC pixel-1 year-1)						Harris et al (2021) model + satellite data Global Forest Review, 30 m resolution, yearly data 2001-2022 Monthly/3-hourly fluxes (incl. N2O and CH4) could be derived from CAMS, but this is at a very coarse spatial resolution (1.9° x 3.75°)	JULES output (for point runs in CSAs), although not from all runs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Carbon stock in harvested wood products (tons/m³)	Global Core Set 3 Forest Europe 1.4	Increase		FRA Forest Europe	NFI (data process); MITECO (Spain) Modelled data, forest districts statistics (RO)		JULES output (for point runs in CSAs), although not from all runs PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data (for simulated EFTs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Changes in total forest biomass carbon stocks (tons/year) / Greenhouse Gas Fluxes from Forests (Gt CO2e)		Decrease		World Resources Institute/ Global Forest Review	NFI (data process); MITECO (Spain) Modelled NFI (RO)		WRI model (see here) with 30 m resolution PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

1166 indicators

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Regulation & maintenance	Protective services	Protective functions	Forest area designated to protect soil, water, and other forest ecosystem functions (=Protective forest area) (ha, %)	Global Core set 11 Forest Europe 5.1	No decrease	Potective forest areas maintain soil organic matter, and regulate water cycles, enhancing C sequestration capacity and mitigating C loss, ultimately promoting ecosystem resilience and C storage. An increase of the protective forest area increases the forest's resilience against changes in climate and related disturbances caused by avalanches, floods, etc., and thus increases the C mitigation potential of the forest area.	FRA Forest Europe Eurostat	FMP Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forest Service; Land use shapefiles; Regional Web Map Service; PNOA; Nature 2000 Net-work (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Forest Health	Degradation	Deforestation (ha)		Decrease	Deforestation is a major source of carbon emissions, as trees are logged and the forest area is converted to other land uses, such as agriculture or urbanization. Much of the carbon stored in the soil is released into the atmosphere, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. Thus, a decrease of deforestation contributes to maintaining the carbon mitigation potential of the forest area.	EEA FISE World Resources Institute/ Global Forest Review	Land use shapefiles; Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Degraded forest area (ha, %) FE Def: Persistent reduction or loss of land biological and economic productivity, adversely affecting the multiple provisions of forest ecosystem goods and services.	Global Core Set 7 Forest Europe 2.5	Decrease	Degraded forests are forests that have been damaged by illegal logging, fire and other damaging agents leading to decreasing levels of carbon sequestration and storage decreasing the forest carbon mitigation potential of a forest.	FRA Forest Europe World Resources Institute/ Global Forest Review	Land use shapefiles; Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain)	Global Forest Review We need to be sure that "no forest" is not due to clear-cutting activities where forest will regenerate but was caused by large-scale degrading events where forests do not regenerate so soon. Otherwise, misleading interpretations as published by Ceccherini et al. 2020		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Illegal logging (m³/ha)		Decrease	Illegal logging can lead to degradation, which reduces the carbon storage capacity of forests. Illegal logging can also lead to soil erosion, decreased water quality, and loss of biodiversity. These factors contribute to climate change and reduce the ability of forests to mitigate its effects.	EEA	Local Forest Administration			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Disturbances	Natural losses (Tree mortality) (m³/ha) - on forest available for wood supply - on total forest area	Part of Forest Europe 3.1	Decrease	Natural losses on forest available for wood supply can reduce the overall biomass available for carbon sequestration. This impacts the forest's capacity to mitigate carbon dioxide levels by limiting its ability to absorb and store carbon.	Forest Europe DFDE	PNOA (Data process) (Spain)		Output data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Changes in tree cover density (%) →we need to be sure not to include here changes due to planned FMP but only from disturbances	Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg.	No negative changes	Negative changes in tree cover density caused by disturbances directly reduce the forest's carbon mitigation potential. As tree cover density decreases, the forest's capacity to sequester carbon through photosynthesis diminishes, leading to less carbon stored in biomass and soil. This results in increased carbon dioxide emissions, exacerbating climate change and decreasing stand resilience. Restoring tree cover density post-disturbance is crucial for maintaining the forest's ability to mitigate carbon emissions and contribute to climate change mitigation efforts.	Landsat data archive, see Turubanova et al 2023	Regional Web Map Service; PNOA and NFI (data process) (Spain)	Sentinel-2 Copernicus High-Resolution Layer Tree Cover Density There are also separate maps for tree cover change, which can be used to filter regions where canopy loss has occurred in the last ~10 years. ~10/100 m resolution 2012, 2015, 2018	3D-CMCC output data for simulated forest types	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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			Forest area with damage/disturbances (ha, %) caused by - severe weather events - other abiotic agents (not fire)	Global Core Set 6 Forest Europe 2.4	Decrease	Forest damages/disturbances lead to huge amounts of deadwood. Particularly forest fires lead to an immediate release of large amounts of carbon into the atmosphere. An increase of forest area damaged/disturbed decreases the forest carbon mitigation potential of the living forest biomass and forest soils and contributes to climate change.	DFDE FRA Forest Europe	FMP Regional Web Map Service; PNOA (Spain)	Landsat/FORWIND, 2000-2018. Could be extended to subsequent years/regions if on-the-ground observations are available Disturbances to long-term forest cover can be derived from the "Forest area" datasets. Without near real-time land cover data the other causes might only be assessed by the Dynamic World Sentinel -2 dataset available on Google Earth Engine →we need to be sure not to include here changes due to clearcutting		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area with damage/disturbances (ha, %) caused by - insects and diseases - other biotic agents like wildlife and grazing	Global Core Set 6 Forest Europe 2.4	Decrease		DFDE FRA Forest Europe	FMP Regional government, MITECO; Regional Web Map Service, PNOA (Spain)	Landsat/ DEFID2, 1963-2021 Could be extended to subsequent years/regions if on-the-ground observations are available		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area damaged by fire (ha, %)	Global Core Set 6 Forest Europe 2.4 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Decrease		FRA Forest Europe DFDE INForest	FMP Regional government, MITECO; Regional Web Map Service and PNOA (Spain)	Annual fire damage could be assessed by Burned area datasets e.g. Copernicus Burnt Area, ESA Fire MODIS/Sentinel-3 C3S/ Burned Area, ~250-300 m resolution, daily 2001-2022		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Soil erosion (ha, %)		Decrease	Soil erosion can lead to decarbonization losses by disrupting carbon storage in soils. It removes organic matter rich in carbon, reducing soil fertility and microbial activity, which decreases the carbon sequestration capacity. This results in a net loss of carbon from the ecosystem.		National soil map; national soil erosion inventory (Spain)	Erosion in forestland - ESDAC - European Soil Data Centre ESDAC Global Soil Erosion (Modelled) ~25km, 2001, 2012		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Area of forest dominated by <u>invasive</u> , introduced tree species (ha, %)	Part of Forest Europe 4.4	Decrease	In some cases, invasive species may increase carbon storage by growing faster or having higher wood density. However, they can also negatively impact carbon storage and sequestration by altering soil chemistry and microbial communities, reducing leaf litter, and altering nutrient cycling. Therefore, managing forests to decrease the area dominated by invasive, introduced species may have positive effects on the forest's carbon mitigation potential.	FRA Forest Europe	Regional government; MITECO; Regional Web Map Service and PNOA (data processing) (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Browsing pressure (No deer/ha)		Decrease	High deer populations can exert significant browsing pressure on trees and saplings, especially those of preferred species. This browsing can inhibit regeneration and tree growth also altering forest structure,		Hunting authority			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Regulation & maintenance	Damage regulation	Damage response	Red deer and roe deer shootings (No/ha)		Increase	reducing the overall carbon sequestration potential of the forest.		Hunting authority			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Protection measures against browsing (EUR/ha)		Increase	Individual stem protection and fencing of stems or young stands secures regeneration and tree growth, which contributes to maintaining or enhancing the carbon mitigation potential of a forest.		FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Salvage logging (m³/ha)		Increase	The removal of damaged, infected and dead trees can help to store carbon in wood products and reduce the risk of carbon emissions from decomposing trees. However, the overall carbon mitigation potential of a forest is always negatively impacted by a damaging event.		FMP		PICUS output for simulated forest types	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Removal and disposal of infected/infested trees (m³/ha)		Increase			FMP		PICUS output for simulated forest types	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Damage clearing (EUR /ha)		Increase			FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest restoration/ forest recovery (ha, share of damaged or degraded forest area restored)		Increase	Restoring degraded forests can help to increase their mitigation potential by C sequestration and storage in forest soils and woody biomass, regaining ES. However, the C mitigation potential of a re-stored forest may not reach the pre-degradation level of C sequestration for several decades.	(WRI)	Regional government Forestry Service; MITECO; Regional Web Map Service and PNOA (data process) (Spain)		WRI: There are currently no global-scale geo-spatial data sets that allow measurement of structure, ecosystem, biodiversity, carbon of forest recovery directly or by proxy.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Recovery efforts (reforestation costs) (EUR/ha)		Increase	Recovery efforts involve planting new trees and managing invasive species, increasing the C sequestration potential of the forest. Recovery efforts can also help to enhance carbon sequestration in soils by reducing erosion, improving soil quality, and increasing organic matter content.		FMP Regional government Forestry Service; MITECO (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Damage monitoring (aerial surveys, ground-based surveys) (EUR/ha)		Increase	(Rapid) damage monitoring can help to detect damages early, which can allow for prompt response (countermeasures like salvage logging, reforestation with site-adapted species) to mitigate the impacts of the damage and prevent the loss of C.		FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Use of chemical, biological or technical precautionary measures (EUR/ha)		Increase	The use of chemical, biological or technical precautionary or counter-measures can help to maintain or restore the health of a forest by controlling or mitigating the impacts of pests, diseases, or other disturbances that can reduce the forest's C sequestration potential.		FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest Health	Health and Vitality	Soil condition per soil type -Acidity: pH scale; units -CEC: cmol/kg -C/N ratio -Organic C Density: g/kg, t/ha -Base saturation: % (sum base cations/CEC)*100	Forest Europe 2.2	Increase towards optimization	Healthy soil condition in forests is crucial for stability, productivity, water protection, and carbon sequestration influencing tree growth, species composition, and resilience to pests and diseases, thus aiding in decarbonisation efforts.	ICP Forests Forest Europe	National soil map	ICP Forests Database (Level I, Level II)	Input data for PICUS	<input type="checkbox"/>
Defoliation (%)	Forest Europe 2.3 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Decrease			Defoliation can lead to decarbonization losses by reducing photosynthetic activity and C sequestration capacity. It disrupts the C cycle by decreasing foliage, limiting C uptake, potentially increasing C release through reduced biomass, altering eco-system dynamics, leading to net C loss	ICP Forests Forest Europe		ICP Forests Database	3D-CMCC output data for simulated forest types	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

23 indicators

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Supporting	Biodiversity	Regeneration	Share of forest regeneration by natural regeneration (%)	Forest Europe 4.2	tbd	An increase of the share of forest regeneration by site-resilient/ natural regeneration or planting and/or seeding of more than one site-resilient tree species, leads to more structured, stable and healthier trees and thus increases the forest carbon mitigation potential. Giorgio: How do the indicators “interact”, as there could be possible “conflicts” (decreasing/ increasing one or the other)? Should the species count or an analysis of adaptation potential? (e.g. seeding of species to increase mixing in pure forests)	FRA Forest Europe	FMP	-Meteorological data (temperature, precipitation, etc. from CERRA (~5.5 km) -Climate scenario data from CMIP6 -CO ₂ concentration from ISIMIP/CAMS -Forest structure data from Pucher et al. (2022)	Potentially 3D-CMCC-FEM could provide output	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Share of natural regeneration not site-adapted (%)		decrease		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Share of forest regeneration by planting and/or seeding (%)	Forest Europe 4.2	tbd		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		Potentially 3D-CMCC-FEM could provide output	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Share of forest area with 1, 2-5, 6+ tree species regenerated	Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	tbd		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Share of regeneration area where invasive species dominate (%)		decrease		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Share of forest area with site resilient tree species change after cutting or after forest damage (ha, %)		Increase		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Survival rate of regenerated trees/saplings (%)		Increase		Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Supporting	Biodiversity	Naturalness		Change in area of primary forest area (%)	Global Core Set 5 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	No decrease	Primary forests, and also forests undisturbed by man, generally have the highest carbon stocks unless they are in the decay stage. Therefore, an increase of the primary forest area contributes to increase the forest carbon mitigation potential.	FRA	Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service (Spain)	
Forest by classes of naturalness – Share of forest area undisturbed by man of total forest area (ha, %)	Part of Forest Europe 4.3	Increase				Undisturbed forests have very high C stocks unless they are in the decay stage. Therefore, an increase of the forest area undisturbed by man contributes to increase the forest C mitigation potential.	Forest Europe	Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
			Forest by classes of naturalness – Share of semi-natural forest area of total forest area (ha, %)	Part of Forest Europe 4.3	Increase	Semi-natural forests, which are usually managed for timber and other ES have a high C mitigation potential, depending on their management practices. E.g. selective logging can maintain high levels of C stocks and biodiversity. Clearcuts lead to C emissions particularly of forest soils. Increasing of the semi-natural forest area - not on behalf of the forest area undisturbed by man contributes to increase the forest C mitigation potential.	Forest Europe	Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service (Data process); NFI; PNOA (data process) (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest by classes of naturalness – Share of plantations of total forest area (ha, %)	Part of Forest Europe 4.3	tbd	Forest plantations can sequester C quickly, but they may have lower overall C stocks than natural forests as the soil releases C after each clearcutting. However, in-creasing areas of plantations also increase the C mitigation potential in those cases where the plantations were afforested on former non-forest land.	FRA Forest Europe	Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Supporting	Biodiversity	Tree species diversity	Share of forest area with one tree species occurring (%)	Part of Forest Europe 4.1	Decrease (if not naturally)	A decrease of forest area with only one tree species occurring in forests where naturally more species would occur or would contribute to more site resilience against severe damaging events, increases the carbon mitigation potential of the forest area.	Forest Europe	Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)	Tree species identification from space is nontrivial. At best, it's possible to only differentiate between coniferous and deciduous forest without auxiliary information. The Copernicus Pan-European Forest Cover and ESA CCI Global Land Cover datasets (see "Forest area") classifies tree cover in this way. EFT Map	Output data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Share of forest area with 2-5 and with 6+ tree species occurring (%) Degree of mixture?	Part of Forest Europe 4.1	Increase	An increase of forest area classified by 2-5 and 6+ <i>site-resilient</i> tree species occurring, increases the resilience against severe damaging events and thus increases the C mitigation potential of the forest area.	Forest Europe	FMP Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)		Output data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area with <i>site-resilient</i> introduced tree species (ha)		Increase	An increase of forest area with introduced tree species which are <i>site-resilient</i> in the sense of coping better with climate change, increases the resilience against severe damaging agents and thus increases the C mitigation potential of the forest area.		FMP Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Threatened tree species (No)	Part of Forest Europe 4.8	Tbd	Loss of threatened tree species diminishes FES, such as C sequestration and habitat provision, potentially leading to decreased C storage capacity and ecosystem instability, resulting in decarbonization losses.	Forest Europe	FMP Regional Nature Conservation Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Supporting	Biodiversity	Structural diversity	Multi-layer stands (ha) or share of multi-layer stands (%)	Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	Multi-layer stands accumulate more organic matter, capture solar radiation and C dioxide efficiently, retain C for longer periods, promote soil C storage, and minimize C loss during disturbances like storms as their resilience is higher. This makes multi-layer stands effective in sequestering and storing c compared to single-layer stands which are more prone to decarbonization losses. An increase of forest area with multi-layer stands thus increases the C mitigation potential of the forest area.		FMP NFI, Farm-scale FMP (Spain)	Should be possible by Laser/Lidar, see above		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Single-layer stands (ha, %)		Decrease			FMP NFI, Farm-scale FMP (Spain)	Should be possible by Laser/Lidar, see above		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Stand density (No of trees/ha)		Tbd	Higher density usually means more C sequestration, but optimal levels vary. Very dense or sparse stands negatively affect C sequestration rates. Thinning can enhance growth and resilience.		NFI, Farm-scale FMP (Spain)	Should be possible by Laser/Lidar, see above	Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility		
			Stand age (Years/Age classes, %)	Forest Europe 1.3 EU Nature Restoration Law	Increase	An increase of the stand age increases the carbon stored in the forest stand next to carbon stored in living biomass, thus contributing to increase the overall forest carbon mitigation potential.	Forest Europe	FMP NFI (Data process), Farm-scale FMP (Spain)	2 datasets for forest age, using a combination of modelling and RS at: -0.1-degree resolution -1 km resolution Data download here BGI Forest Age, Upscaled from in-situ data, ~1km, 2010 GFAD is an alternative dataset, but has a spatial resolution of 0.5°	Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Canopy height (m)			Taller trees typically have higher C storage capacities but forests with diverse height distributions are more resilient to disturbances thus having an overall higher C sequestration potential.			JULES output data		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
			Tree height distribution (%)		Tbd	Tree height distribution can influence decarbonization efforts by affecting forest structure and carbon storage. Taller trees typically have higher carbon storage capacities but forests with diverse height distributions are more resilient to disturbances thus having a higher carbon sequestration potential.		FMP NFI (Data process), Farm-scale FMP (Spain)	GDI canopy height (GDI ISS), ~30m, yearly, 2019 This dataset does not exceed beyond 52° N. Alternatively, a newer dataset based on GEDI + Sentinel-2 (10 m) data was developed for 2020 observations by Lang et al (2023), but tiling artifacts exist at higher latitudes	Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Provisioning	Biodiversity	Deadwood	Deadwood (standing) (m³/ha)	Forest Europe 4.5 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	An increase of deadwood increases the C stored in the forest stand next to C stored in living biomass and forest soils, thus contributes to increase the overall forest C mitigation potential until the deadwood decays.	FRA Forest Europe	Farm-scale FMP (Spain)		Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
					Deadwood (lying) (m³/ha)	EU Nature Restoration Law	Increase		FRA Forest Europe	Farm-scale FMP (Spain)		Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
					Deadwood decomposition stage		Tbd	In early stages, deadwood acts as a C sink, sequestering C. However, as decomposition progresses, C is released back into the atmosphere, impacting the forest's ability to mitigate C dioxide levels.		Farm-scale FMP (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Biodiversity	Forest reproductive material	Tree populations managed for genetic conservation (ha)	Part of Forest Europe 4.6	Increase	An increase of the units/area for site-resilient forest reproductive material leads to more stable and healthier trees and thus increases the forest carbon mitigation potential of the forests established with that material.	Forest Europe	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Technology centres, universities nurseries (Spain)				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Potential for the production of Forest Reproductive Material (Number of units/area)	Part of Forest Europe 4.6	Increase		Forest Europe	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Technology centres, universities nurseries (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Biodiversity protection	Conservation	Protected forest area (ha, %) - No active intervention - Minimum intervention - Conservation through active management - Protection of landscapes	Global Core Set 4 Subindicator of SDG 15.2.1 Forest Europe 4.9 Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	Protected forest areas generally have a higher C mitigation potential than forests available for wood supply. Trees in protected forests are able to grow larger and live longer, allowing them to sequester more C over time. However, in cases when very old protected forests collapse and regenerate, sustainably managed forests can even sequester more C than protected forests due to active management practices such as selective harvesting and site-resilient reforestation.	FRA Forest Europe INForest FISE	FMP Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest inside Natura2000 (%)	Draft EU Forest Monitoring Reg	Increase	The specific carbon mitigation potential of forests within the Natura 2000 network will depend on the particular characteristics of each forest, including forest type, stand age, management practices, and local environmental conditions. However, protected forest areas generally have a higher C mitigation potential than forests available for wood supply (see indicator protected forest area).	FISE	FMP Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

¹ Site-resilient species are not necessarily only native species, but could also be introduced, non-invasive species, which cope better with climate change induced changes (drought, storms etc)
28 indicators

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Forest management	Forest management practices	Forest area with continuous cover management (ha, %)		Increase	Continuous cover management can enhance carbon sequestration by allowing for the maintenance of a continuous forest cover, which promotes long-term carbon storage through the growth and accumulation of trees in all age classes.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)	Near real-time land cover datasets necessary to identify such forest areas. →Dynamic World Sentinel-2 dataset as a potential means to detect and analyse such areas. The high spatial resolution (10 m) and 5-day revisit time afforded by Sentinel-2 would be our best option.		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area with no harvest management (ha, %)		tbd	Lack of management may lead to increased vulnerability to disturbances like wildfires or pests, and loss of biodiversity, resulting in decreased ecosystem resilience and C storage capacity. On the other hand, non-managed forest areas often represent natural, intact ecosystems that support high levels of biodiversity and the areas can serve as C sinks, storing significant amounts of carbon in biomass and soil organic matter.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Adaptive forest management (ha, %)		Increase	Forest areas managed with adaptive forest management, aimed at addressing climate change impacts, can enhance decarbonization benefits. By adjusting management practices to mitigate climate-related risks and optimize carbon sequestration potential, these forests contribute to overall carbon storage.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area under integrative forest management (ha, %)		Increase	By promoting multifunctionality including a diverse and resilient forest structure and supporting a range of ES, integrative forest management can help to enhance the long-term carbon sequestration potential.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area under closer to nature management (ha, %)		Increase	By imitating natural processes, promoting structurally rich forests and strengthening the resilience of the ecosystem, closer to nature management supports the carbon mitigation potential of a forest.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area with even-aged management with clearcutting (ha, %)		Decrease	Even so that the carbon stored in the timber may remain in long-lived wood products, the cutting of all trees in a stand results in the loss of carbon stored in both the aboveground biomass (branches, leaves) and belowground biomass (roots and soil organic matter) as that biomass either decompose in the stand or is used for energy production, resulting in overall decarbonization losses.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service; NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Forest area with even-aged management with shelterwood (ha, %)		tbd	Forest areas managed with even-aged management using shelterwood systems can have mixed effects on decarbonization. While shelterwood systems retain some canopy cover, promoting natural regeneration and maintaining ecosystem functions, they may still result in temporary reductions in carbon storage during harvest rotations.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service; Regional Web Map Service (Data process); NFI; PNOA (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator Incl. measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
			Selective harvesting (ha, %)		Increase	Selective harvesting can have a lower impact on the carbon mitigation potential of a forest than clear-cutting. This is because the removal of only a portion of the trees allows the remaining trees to continue to grow and sequester carbon and also the soil carbon is not affected negatively.		FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Reduced impact logging (ha, %)		Increase	Reduced impact logging involves the use of specialized equipment and techniques that minimize soil disturbance, protect remaining trees from damage, and promote the regeneration of the forest which maintains the carbon mitigation potential of a forest.		FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Agroforestry areas (ha, %) (e.g. forest pastures like Dehesa, Montado)		tbd	Agroforestry systems can have higher carbon sequestration rates compared to conventional agriculture or monoculture forestry due to the mix of species and the presence of perennial crops. Pasture grasses in combination with tree and shrub cover can increase soil organic matter, which can lead to more carbon sequestration in the soil compared to pasture only.		FMP Ministry of Agriculture, Regional Government (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Area of short rotation forest (for bioenergy) (ha, %)		tbd	Short rotation forests can have mixed effects on decarbonization. While they offer rapid biomass growth and C sequestration potential, frequent harvesting cycles may reduce overall C storage compared to longer rotation periods. Proper management is crucial to balance carbon uptake and sustainable biomass production.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Area of forest with coppice with standards (ha, %)		tbd	Coppicing with standards can enhance decarbonization benefits by promoting both short-term C uptake through regrowth of coppice shoots and long-term C storage through the growth of standard trees. This practice maintains forest productivity contributing to overall carbon storage.		FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Area of forests coppice (or other traditional management types) (ha, %)	Part of Forest Europe 4.2	tbd	Coppicing can enhance the carbon storage potential of a forest by promoting the growth of a dense network of young trees. This can increase the carbon uptake of the forest.	Forest Europe	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Management intensity (increment/fellings %)	Forest Europe 3.1	tbd	Forest management intensity, represented by the share of fellings of the increment, significantly impacts decarbonization efforts. Intensive management practices, such as high harvesting rates, can lead to reduced C sequestration potential and biodiversity loss, resulting in decarbonization losses. Sustainable harvesting practices aim to balance timber extraction with the maintenance of ecosystem integrity and carbon sequestration capacity.	Forest Europe	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)		Input data for PICUS and 3D-CMCC-FEM	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator including measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility	
Provisioning	Clean water	Watersheds	Quantity of groundwater within a forest watershed (m ³ /ha)		Increase	Forests located in watersheds with adequate water supply can potentially have a higher carbon mitigation potential compared to those in watersheds with water scarcity as they are less likely to experience drought stress, which make them more resilient to drought, wildfire, pest and bark beetle outbreaks.		FMP Spanish Geological and Mining Institute (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Share of forest area in watershed (%)		tbd			Regional Government Forestry Service; water resources confederations (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
			Quality of water (level of nutrients, sediments, contamination, pH) (mg/L)		Increase		Clean water is necessary for healthy plant growth. Contaminants such as pollutants and sediment can limit the C sequestration potential of the forest. Clear-cutting and forest damaging events can result in soil erosion and sedimentation in water bodies, which can affect water quality and, in turn, impact the forest's potential to mitigate C.		Local environment authority water resources confederations (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Food	NWGs	Non-wood goods (metric tonnes)	Forest Europe 3.3	Increase	The extraction of non-wood goods can have a negative impact on the carbon mitigation potential of a forest if they are extracted in huge amounts, otherwise rather marginal.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	FES as such	Available FES		Presence/absence of a certain forest ecosystem service		tbd	Forests provide a wide range of FES, incl. C sequestration, water regulation, recreation, eco-tourism among others. Information on the presence, absence, or importance of FES directly impacts decarbonization benefits. High importance services like C sequestration and water regulation enhance decarbonization efforts by mitigating climate change impacts, while their absence or lower importance can lead to loss of these benefits, hindering decarbonization goals.		FMP Regional Nature Conservation Service; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Value of marketed services on forest and OWL (Ecological, biospheric, social services) (Euro)	Forest Europe 3.4	Increase	The marketing of FES can have a positive effect on the carbon mitigation potential of a forest. By valuing and marketing the FES, forest owners and managers may be incentivized to manage their forests towards maximizing carbon sequestration.	FRA Forest Europe	FMP			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Carbon credits sold (one per every ton of CO ₂ the forest sequesters)		Increase	Carbon credits are a way for organizations and individuals to offset their C emissions by investing in activities that reduce greenhouse gas emissions or remove C dioxide from the atmosphere. Forest owners can contribute to C mitigation potential by selling carbon credits generated through sustainable forest management sequestering carbon from the atmosphere.		FMP MITECO (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

7 indicators

ES Class	FES	Issue	Indicator including measurement units	Reference to international indicator set	Positive effect on C mitigation	Explanation of decarbonisation benefit or loss	National data source	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility	
Cultural	Stewardship	Certification	Forest area under an independently verified forest management certification system (ha, %) Giorgio: Relevant, as implies a "responsibility measure" of the forest managers – active action for mitigation/adaptation	Global Core Set 20 Forest Europe qualitative ind.	Increase	Independently verified forest certification can be an effective tool for promoting sustainable forest management practices that enhance the ability of forests to sequester C and mitigate climate change. Thus, an increase of the certified forest area can have a positive impact on the forest C mitigation potential	FSC PEFC FRA Forest Europe INForest	FSC PEFC			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Management plans	Share of forest area under a long-term forest management plan (ha, %)	Global Core Set 19 Forest Europe qualitative ind.	Increase	A long-term forest management plan focuses towards SFM practices and can help to maintain forest resilience in the face of climate change. As the climate changes, forests may be impacted by drought, wildfire, and other disturbances that can affect their ability to sequester carbon. A long-term management plan may also include strategies to increase forest resilience, such as by planting more site-resilient tree species, managing forest water resources, and reducing soil erosion. Thus, such a plan can help to maintain and enhance the carbon mitigation potential of a forest.	FRA Forest Europe INForest	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Logistics	Length of forest roads (km, m/ha)		tbd	Forest roads provide access to remote forest areas and facilitate SFM practices such as selective harvesting or reduced-impact logging of timber leading to carbon stored in harvested wood products. On the negative side, forest roads can contribute to deforestation and carbon emissions by providing access to illegal logging in some areas. Forest roads also fragment forest areas, which may lead to decreasing FES.	National forest road inventories	FMP Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)	Open street map, yearly			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Investments	Investments in Forestry (ISIC/NACE 02) (EUR)	Forest Europe 6.4	Increase	Investments in forestry can have a significant impact on the carbon mitigation potential of a forest. By providing funding for maintaining and enhancing FES, SFM practices, reforestation and afforestation efforts, and forest-based carbon offset projects, investments can help to increase the carbon storage capacity of the forest.	FRA Forest Europe	MITECO; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Public financial support and private investments for FES (EUR/ha)		Increase			FMP MITECO; Regional Government Forestry Service (Spain)			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Livelihood	Employment	Employment in Forestry (ISIC/ NACE 02) (No)	Forest Europe 6.5	tbd	The impact of employment in forestry on the carbon mitigation potential of a forest depends on the specific management practices. If well-educated staff apply SFM practices that enhance the carbon storage capacity of the forest, this contributes positively to the carbon mitigation potential.	FRA Forest Europe Statistical Offices				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Subsistence	Financial contribution of the forest to the forest owner's livelihood (EUR)		Increase	The financial contribution of forests to forest owner's livelihood can help incentivize SFM practices which can contribute to the carbon mitigation potential.					<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Life-long learning	Education	Number of forest managers attending advanced training courses (No) Giorgio: Relevant for OptFor-EU stakeholder involvement		Increase	Attending advanced training courses can make a difference for the C mitigation potential of a forest by improving forest managers' knowledge and skills in SFM practices, providing access to new technologies and innovative management practices, and facilitating the sharing of knowledge with the staff.	Chamber of Agricultures				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Climate indicators to quantify biophysical impacts of forest management measures on regional and local climate conditions

There are many interactions between forest change and climate change. Forest management measures are needed for climate mitigation and adaptation. Forest management measures such as forest cover change through re-/afforestation, forest conversion, irrigation, etc affect carbon fluxes and storage. At the same time, they have direct effects on the regional and local climate conditions through biophysical processes, influencing the exchange of momentum, energy, water and other substances between land and atmosphere. For example, the roughness length of forests affects turbulent heat fluxes and atmospheric mixing, and thus the distribution of heat and moisture in the atmosphere, and precipitation patterns. Forest modifications can change the surface radiation budget by changing the land surface albedo or cloud cover. Forests can lead to local cooling through evapotranspiration. Such effects depend on background climate conditions, on local soil and vegetation properties, and they interact in complex ways. The biophysical impacts of forests on regional and local climate, in turn, feedback on carbon fluxes and storage.

The table below presents a range of indicators which quantify the ability of forests to mitigate climatic changes. These refer mainly to biophysical effects and feedback of forest on the local and regional climate. In terms of FES, they could be seen as regional and local climate regulation. They are based on essential climate variables for atmosphere and land (ECVs)

Table S2: Overview of climate-related indicators structured along Classes of Ecosystem Services (ES), Forest Ecosystem Services (FES), associated climate system compartments, Essential Climate Variables, data sources as well as input for and output of the forest models (PICUS, 3D-CMCC-FEM), regional climate models (REMO, RegCM), land surface models (JULES) and the DSS as basis for a range of Essential Forest-Climate Indicators to amend the set of Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators (EFMI).

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Surface Atmosphere	Temperature (surface, air)	Temperature [K] or [°C] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual/seasonal/monthly/daily mean/minimum/ maximum temperature; Annual/seasonal/monthly/daily temperature range Indicators for climate change and extremes are e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of frost days/yr Number of heat days/yr Heat spell duration, etc. 	ETCCDI climate change indices Climpact Indices	If there is an increase or decrease in near surface air temperature, depends on the forest management practices, and additional factors, such as geographical location, background climate conditions, soil conditions, vegetation properties etc. Near surface air temperature has profound and widespread impacts on human and natural systems, e.g. affecting forest ecosystems, human health, agriculture, water availability, energy demand and much more. It affects the fluxes of heat, momentum, water vapour and trace species between land and atmosphere.	Near surface air temperatures affect carbon fluxes in forests. Increasing temperatures could increase or reduce the carbon sequestration potential. If forest management practices lead e.g. to a reduction of heat extremes, this could lead to an increase in carbon sequestration.	Local measurements AEMET (Spain)	CERRA: 1984-2021, 5.5 km & 3-hourly resolution ERA5-Land: 1950-2023, ~10 km & hourly resolution 2m temperature is available from both datasets to compute these statistics Available on SIMAVI server from CERRA Reanalysis, but not for extremes. Also, Land Surface Temperature (monthly mean) is available from MODIS at 1 km, 2000-2022	Validation RS data required JULES input data (but subdaily) RegCM output data REMO output data on near surface air temperature (2 m above ground) up to hourly time scale (incl. mean, min, max)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Surface temperature				JULES surface temperature is probably too simplified to be useful	JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
				Duration (time) of extreme winter or summer warming events [consecutive days]	ETCCDI climate change indices	Extreme winter events can cause snow melt and expose vegetation to freezing temperatures, leading to vegetation damage in the winter. Heat waves in summer increase the evapotranspiration from the soil causing water stress for the tree and wilting in extreme cases. Heat waves also increase the transpiration of vegetation and stomatal closure and reduced photosynthesis. In addition, the damaged vegetation leads to a reduced LAI.	In winter damaged vegetation has been shown to have reduced productivity/ carbon sequestration during the following growing season. Extreme summer warming events lead to growth reduction or failure.	AEMET (Spain)		RegCM output data REMO output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Intensity (time+temperature change) of extreme winter or summer warming events [K] or [°C]	ETCCDI climate change indices	Extreme winter events can cause snow melt and expose vegetation to freezing temperatures, leading to vegetation damage in winter. Heat waves in summer increase the evapotranspiration from the soil causing water stress for the tree and wilting in extreme cases. Heat waves also increase the transpiration of vegetation, stomatal closure and reduced photosynthesis. In addition, the damaged vegetation leads to a reduced LAI.	The damaged vegetation has been shown to have reduced productivity (carbon sequestration) during the following growing season. Extreme summer warming events lead to growth reduction or failure.	AEMET (Spain)		RegCM output data REMO output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Upper-air- Atmosphere	Temperature (upper air)	Vertical temperature profile [K] or [°C]	-	Forests affect vertical temperature profiles. Temperature profiles above forests could be interesting to look at. F.ex. they affect turbulent heat fluxes, atmospheric stability, convection, cloud cover etc.	The vertical temperature profile influences the forest carbon cycle by affecting rates of photosynthesis, respiration and decomposition	FLIUXNET data? AEMET (Spain)	CERRA has temperature data on 11 height levels between 15 – 500 m, or 29 pressure levels between 1000 – 1 hPa	Validation RS data required RegCM output data REMO output data in up to 49 vertical levels, up to 6 hourly time steps	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Surface Atmosphere	Precipitation	Precipitation [mm] -Annual -seasonal -monthly -daily => The selection should be done with the stakeholders according to their needs	Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) takes into acc. precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (PET) for assessing drought conditions.	Forests can influence regional precipitation (rain and snow) patterns (also in remote regions). Changes in summer and winter precipitation affect decarbonization rates positively or negatively depending on the site-resilience of the forest tree species.	Precipitation amount affects the forest C cycle by regulating soil moisture levels, which in turn influence plant growth, decomposition rates, and microbial activity. Adequate precipitation can enhance C uptake through photosynthesis, while droughts may limit growth and increase C loss through respiration.	Local measurements AEMET (Spain)	CERRA or one of the following satellite datasets: -NASA IMERG (Final Run): 2000 – 2021, ~10 km & 30 min resolution -JAXA GSMaP: 2000 – 2023, ~10 km & hourly resolution Available on SIMAVI server from CERRA Reanalysis	JULES input data (but needs to be subdaily) RegCM output data REMO output data on total precipitation, up to 6-hourly time step	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Indicators for climate change and extremes - Annual or monthly maximum 1-day precipitation [mm] - Number of days per year with precipitation > 20 mm	ETCCDI climate change indices Climpact Indices	Increased high precipitation days can lead to more frequent flooding, altered soil moisture levels, and changes in vegetation patterns, influencing local climate conditions and hydrological cycles.	Excessively wet conditions may lead to waterlogging, decreased root oxygen availability, and increased decomposition rates, potentially offsetting C gains.	Local measurements AEMET (Spain)	CERRA or one of the following satellite datasets: -NASA IMERG (Final Run): 2000 – 2021, ~10 km & 30 min resolution -JAXA GSMaP: 2000 – 2023, ~10 km & hourly resolution	RegCM output data REMO output data on total precipitation, up to 6-hourly time step	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Surface Atmosphere	Water vapour (surface air)	Daily water vapour - as relative humidity [%] - as specific humidity [kg/kg]	-	Forests affect near surface water vapour e.g. through evapotranspiration, roughness length, etc., interacting with forest effects on wind and temperature. Influence on fog formation. The near surface air humidity e.g. affects the comfort and health of humans, livestock and wildlife, or the occurrence of plant disease.	Water vapor affects the forest carbon cycle by influencing plant transpiration rates and soil moisture levels. In-creased water vapor can enhance transpiration, promoting plant growth and carbon uptake, while also affecting microbial activity and decomposition rates in the soil.	Local measurements AEMET (Spain)	E-OBS has 2m relative humidity CERRA has 2m relative humidity, air, and dew point temperature.	Validation RS data required JULES input data (but needs to be subdaily) RegCM output data REMO output data on e.g. near surface humidity, up to hourly time step PICUS output data 3D-CMCC output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Upper-Air- Atmosphere	Water vapour (upper air)	Water vapour - Vertically integrated water vapour content [kg/m2] - tropospheric water vapour profiles,	-	Forests influence the transport of moisture in the atmosphere, affecting cloud cover, precipitation (also in remote regions)	Vertically integrated water vapor influences the forest C cycle by regulating atmospheric moisture availability. Higher levels of vertically integrated water vapor can enhance plant transpiration rates, affecting water stress levels, plant growth, and ultimately carbon uptake in forest ecosystems.		CERRA has specific humidity data on 11 height levels between 15 – 500 m, or 29 pressure levels between 1000 – 1 hPa	RegCM output data REMO output data on e.g. vertically integrated water vapour content, up to hourly time step	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Upper-Air-Atmosphere	Clouds	Cloud optical depth	-	Cloud optical depth influences regional climate by affecting the balance between incoming solar radiation and outgoing longwave radiation. High optical depth can enhance warming by trapping heat, while low optical depth may lead to cooling by allowing more heat to escape into space. Cloud properties also affect e.g. radiation and precipitation.	Cloud optical depth affects the carbon cycle by influencing photosynthesis and respiration rates. High optical depth reduces photosynthesis by limiting sunlight, while low optical depth enhances photosynthesis.	AEMET (Spain)	The ESA-CCI product family offers satellite datasets of cloud properties between 1995 – 2012 & 2017 – present day, at spatiotemporal resolutions of ~10 km (daily) or ~50 km (monthly). Variables provided: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud cover area fraction • Cloud-top pressure • Cloud-top height • Cloud droplet effective radius • Cloud optical depth at 550nm • Cloud liquid water path • Cloud ice water path Alternatively, the CLARA product family offers more continuous satellite coverage (1982 – present day), albeit at a coarser resolution (~25 km, daily/ monthly)	RegCM output data REMO output data on cloud cover (In REMO, we are modeling the cloud cover (in multiple layers), the liquid water & ice content in clouds, cloud max. height, and we can derive the cloud forcing on the surface energy budget)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Surface Atmosphere	Surface Wind	Surface Wind Speed and direction [m/s]	-	The roughness length of forests influences speed and direction of wind. Surface wind speed and direction influence regional climates by affecting temperature, precipitation patterns, and atmospheric circulation. Higher speeds enhance evaporation, altering humidity and rainfall distribution. Wind direction determines where weather systems travel, impacting local temperatures and storm tracks. These factors collectively shape regional climate variations.	Higher wind speeds enhance CO ₂ exchange between the atmosphere and terrestrial or marine ecosystems, potentially altering CO ₂ concentrations.	Local measurements AEMET (Spain)	CERRA has 10 m wind speed and direction Available on SIMAVI server from CERRA Reanalysis (only wind speed; to discuss how the direction should be presented)	Validation RS data required RegCM input data JULES input data (but needs to be subdaily) RegCM output data REMO output data on e.g. surface wind speed at 10 m height	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Maximum wind speed (m/s)		High wind speeds in forests can cause tree damage, uprooting, and canopy disruption, altering microclimates and influencing forest structure		AEMET (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
				Wind gust (m/s)		Wind gusts in forests can cause tree damage, uprooting, and canopy disruption, altering microclimates, influencing forest structure, and potentially triggering disturbances like blowdowns.		AEMET (Spain)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Biosphere	Albedo	Land surface albedo -monthly -daily	-	Land surface albedo influences regional climate by regulating the amount of solar radiation reflected or absorbed by the forest cover. High albedo surfaces reflect more sunlight, leading to cooling effects, while low albedo surfaces (dense vegetation, dark green forest cover) absorb more sunlight, contributing to warming in the region. Effect also on land surface radiation budget.	Land surface albedo, influenced by vegetation and snow cover, affects the absorption and reflection of solar radiation. Changes in albedo alter surface temperatures, influencing C uptake by vegetation and soil respiration rates. Darkening surfaces decrease albedo, absorbing more heat and potentially accelerating C release from ecosystems.	AEMET (Spain)	Copernicus Global Land Service Surface Albedo product offers global data at ~1 km resolution every 10 days between 1999-2020 Available on SIMAVI server from MODIS (black-sky albedo, white-sky albedo), monthly at 500 m, 2001-2022, EPSG:4326 – WGS84	Validation RS data required RegCM input data RegCM output data REMO output data JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
				Soil albedo		Soil albedo influences regional climate by affecting surface heat absorption. Darker soils absorb more heat, increasing local temperatures.	Soil albedo influences forest C cycle by affecting temperature. Darker soils absorb more heat, potentially accelerating decomposition rates, altering C storage dynamics.			JULES input data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulator	Biosphere	Leaf area	One-sided green leaf area per unit ground surface area -monthly LA -daily LA	-	High LAI enhances evapotranspiration, cooling the local climate through increased moisture fluxes. Conversely, low LAI reduces evapotranspiration, leading to warmer and drier conditions. LAI also influences albedo, impacting surface energy balance and climate feedbacks.	LA is a critical vegetation structural variable and is essential in the feedback of vegetation to the climate system	Remote sensing (Spain)	Copernicus Global Land Service provides two LAI datasets: • European: 2016 – present, 10 m, daily • Global: 1999 – 2020, 1 km, 10-daily Available on SIMAVI server from MODIS (mean, max, min) monthly at 500 m, 2021-2022 for mean, 2002-2022 for min and max, EPSG: 4326 – WGS84	Validation RS data required RegCM input data JULES input data (for some runs) Input data for PICUS, 3D-CMCC-FEM RegCM output data REMO output data JULES output data (for some runs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Leaf area index (LAI)	LAI= Leaf area (m ²)/ground area (m ²) in broadleaf canopies -monthly LAI -daily LAI			Remote sensing (Spain)	<input type="checkbox"/>			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Surface Atmosphere	Latent and sensible heat fluxes	Daily heat fluxes [W/m ²]	-	High sensible heat fluxes warm the lower atmosphere, potentially leading to increased convection and precipitation. Latent heat fluxes from evapotranspiration affect humidity and cloud formation, impacting regional precipitation patterns and atmospheric circulation (vertical transport of heat & moisture)	Heat fluxes influence the C cycle by affecting ecosystem processes. Sensible heat fluxes regulate temperature, influencing photosynthesis and respiration rates. Latent heat fluxes drive evapotranspiration, impacting water availability for plants and thus affecting C uptake and release through photosynthesis and plant respiration.	Local measurement with sensors?	CERRA-Land offers latent and sensible heat fluxes between 1984 – 2021, at a 5.5 km & hourly resolution	Validation RS data required RegCM output data REMO output data on latent and sensible heat fluxes JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Bowen ratio							<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Hydrosphere	Evapotranspiration	Evapotranspiration [mm/m ²] -monthly -daily	e.g. SPEI Standardised Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index to attest drought conditions	As for latent heat flux. Forests and FMP influence evapotranspiration leading to altered heat & moisture fluxes to the atmosphere which affect the near-surface humidity, temperature, fog formation. In the upper atmosphere cloud formation.	Evapotranspiration, impacts the water availability for plants and thus affecting carbon uptake and release through photosynthesis and plant respiration.	AEMET (Spain)	Satellite datasets: NASA MODIS MOD16: 2000 – 2010, 500 m USGS FEWS NET from VIIRS: offers both potential (i.e. inferred from modelled temperature, pressure, etc. from GDAS using the Pen-man-Monteith eqn or actual (i.e. retrieved from VIIRS imagery). Potential ET is offered as daily data betw. 2008 – 2023, while actual ET is given as monthly or 10-day datasets. Both have a 0.5 km spatial res. Available on SIMAVI server from MODIS (Evapotranspiration and Potential Evapotranspiration) monthly at 500 m, 2000-2022, EPSG:4326 – WGS84	Validation RS data required RegCM output data REMO output data PICUS output data 3D-CMCC-FEM output data JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
				Evaporation of bare soil [mm/m ²]		Evaporation of bare soil influences the soil moisture and therefore the water availability to the plants/trees. Summed up together with evaporation of vegetation and transpiration of vegetation, it affects the near-surface humidity, temperature, fog formation. In the upper atmosphere cloud formation.	Evaporation impacts the water availability for plants and thus affecting carbon uptake and release through photosynthesis and plant respiration.	AEMET (Spain)		REMO output data JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Evaporation of vegetation [mm/m ²]		Evaporation of vegetation is influenced by the LAI (larger surfaces more evaporation) and the vegetation ratio (more vegetation, more evaporation from the vegetation). Summed up with evaporation of bare soil and transpiration of vegetation, it affects the near-surface humidity, temperature, fog formation. In the upper atmosphere cloud formation.	Evaporation of vegetation affects heat and moisture fluxes to the atmosphere and therefore affects the near-surface climate and the ecosystem processes.	AEMET (Spain)		REMO output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Evapotranspiration from canopy (mm/m ²) or (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)		Evapotranspiration from forest canopy regulates local humidity, influences precipitation patterns, moderates temperature.	Evapotranspiration from forest canopy regulates soil moisture, affecting plant growth, decomposition rates, and C uptake, influencing the forest C cycle dynamics.			JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
				Transpiration from vegetation [mm/m ²]		Transpiration from vegetation is influenced by the LAI, the water availability to the plant/tree. Summed up with evaporation from bare soil and evaporation from vegetation, it affects the near-surface humidity, temperature, fog formation. In the upper atmosphere cloud formation	Too high transpiration can lead to wilting of plant due to dehydration, and therefore affects the photosynthesis rate and carbon update/release.	AEMET (Spain)		REMO output data JULES output data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Cryosphere	Snow	Snow -snow coverage [%], -snow depth [m], -snow water equivalent [mm/m ³]	Part of US Climate Change Indicators	Snow water equivalent, depth, and coverage influence regional climates by regulating surface albedo, altering energy balance, and affecting hydrological processes. Changes in these snow parameters impact local temperatures, precipitation patterns, water availability, and ecosystem dynamics, with implications for water resources, and natural hazards such as avalanches and flooding.	Snow water equivalent, depth, and coverage affect the forest carbon cycle by insulating soil, regulating moisture availability, and influencing plant growth. Increased snowpack can enhance soil moisture, promoting tree growth and carbon sequestration, while reduced snow cover can limit water availability, potentially impacting forest productivity and carbon storage.	Local measurements Remote Sensing: AEMET (Spain)	European snow data available from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service for: • Snow cover extent, 2016 – present, 20 m–1 km, daily • Wet/dry snow coverage, 2016–present, 60 m, daily • Snow water equivalent, 2006–present, 5 km, daily CERRA-Land offers: • Snow albedo • Snow density • Snow depth • Snow melt • Snow water equivalent Mountain tourism meteorological and snow indicators for Europe from 1950-2100 derived from reanalysis and climate projections	Validation RS data required JULES input data RegCM output data REMO output data on snow fraction, snow water equivalent	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

ES Class	FES	Climate system compartment	Essential climate variable -ECV	Climate indicators including measurement units (30 year averages)	Reference to international Indicator Set	Explanation of potential regional climate effects in forests	Effect/ Feedback on carbon cycle	WP 3 local data source	WP1 input data WP1 output data	WP2 input data WP2 output data	Suitability	Sensitivity to forest management	Feasibility
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Hydrosphere	Soil moisture	Soil moisture [m] -surface soil moisture -root-zone soil moisture -water holding capacity -soil moisture variability (In REMO, we calculate the soil moisture in m, however, the volumetric soil moisture is usually given in % (= [volume of water (cm ³)/volume of soil (cm ³) × 100]. Often RS data gives [m ³ /m ³], which we could convert into [m] or [%] if we know the depth.)	Proxy indicator for land quality	Forests affect soil moisture e.g. through rooting depth, transpiration, interception etc., with strong impacts on the local and regional water cycle.	Maintaining balanced soil moisture levels that support healthy forest ecosystems can contribute to carbon sequestration and mitigation efforts. However, extreme shifts in soil moisture, whether too wet or too dry, can have adverse consequences for carbon sequestration and ecosystem health.	Natural Soil Inventory (Spain)	EO soil moisture data from: • ESA-CCI SSM : 1978–2022, ~25 km, daily/ monthly. This data is for surface soil moisture (i.e. < 2 cm) only • SMAP L4 data has root-zone soil moisture data, but only offers data betw. 2015–today, at ~9 km, 3-hourly resolution CERRA-Land offers volumetric soil moisture data at 14 depth layers, from 0.01–12 m. The wilting point at each depth is available Soil Water Index available on SIMAVI server from Sentinel 1 and Ascet, monthly at 1 km, 2015-2022, EPSG:4326 – WGS84	Validation RS data required PICUS input data JULES input data (for some runs) RCM output data REMO output data on vertically integrated soil moisture content	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Biosphere	Soil carbon (see EFMI above)	Soil carbon [g/m ² or t/ha]	FRA Forest Europe 1.4	Soil C influences regional climates by regulating carbon levels, affecting temperature, and influencing ecosystem productivity. Changes in soil C stocks alter greenhouse gas emissions, impacting climate stability. Soil C also influences soil fertility and water retention, influencing regional vegetation patterns and hydrological cycles See page 3.	Soil C in forests plays a crucial role in the C cycle by serving as a significant C reservoir. Changes in soil C stocks affect C sequestration rates and overall ecosystem carbon balance in forest environments.		SMAP L4C data includes soil organic carbon estimates, which correlate well with model and forest inventory data (see Endsley et al, 2020) SMAP L4C provides daily global estimates of net ecosystem exchange, at a ~9 km, 3-hourly resolution	Validation RS data required PICUS output data 3D-CMCC-FEM output data for simulated forest types JULES output data (for some runs)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulation & maintenance	Regional climate regulation	Hydrosphere	Groundwater	Groundwater - groundwater level [km] - groundwater volume change [%]		Groundwater influences regional climates by regulating surface water availability, moderating temperature fluctuations, and sustaining ecosystems. Changes in groundwater levels affect streamflow, soil moisture, and vegetation dynamics, influencing local temperatures, precipitation patterns, and hydrological cycles. Groundwater depletion can exacerbate drought conditions and impact water resources, and forest ecosystems.	Groundwater volume changes in forests influence the C cycle by affecting soil moisture levels, which in turn impact tree growth, litter decomposition rates, and soil C storage. Reduced groundwater levels can decrease forest productivity and C sequestration potential.	Local measurements Spanish Geological and Mining Institute (Spain)	GRACE and GRACE-FO data provide datasets on global land water storage between 2002 – 2017 (GRACE), and 2018-2022 (GRACE-FO). All datasets have a spatial resolution of 1°, and a ~monthly temporal resolution	Input data for PICUS , Input data (indirectly) for JULES	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

28 Indicators
In total 130 indicators

Abbreviations

DSS	Decision Support System	FRA	Forest Resource Assessment (of the FAO)
ECV	Essential Climate Variable	ICP Forests	The International Cooperative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests
EFMI	Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators	ISIC/NACE 02	Forestry and Logging
ES	Ecosystem Services	JULES	Land surface model
ESA	European Space Agency	OWL	Other wooded land
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations	PICUS	Forest model
FAWS	Forest Available for Wood Supply	RegCM	Regional Climate Model
FE	Forest Europe	REMO	Regional climate Model
FES	Forest Ecosystem Services	SFM	Sustainable forest management
FISE	Forest Information System of the European Environment Agency		
FMP	Forest Management Plan		

Online survey A for the CSA Stakeholders

Ranking of Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators

Project: OPTimising FOrEst management decisions for a low-carbon, climate resilient future in Europe (OptFor-EU)

Project duration

January 2023 -December 2026

Aim of the project

The primary objective of OptFor-EU, <https://optforeu.eu/>, is to co-develop a user-centred Decision Support System (DSS) with forest managers and other forest stakeholders, that provides them with suitable climate adaptation and mitigation options for science-based optimising forest ecosystem services, including decarbonisation, and enhancing forest resilience and its capacities to mitigate climate change across Europe.

Objective of this survey

Involve forest managers from the Case Study Areas (CSAs) in the selection of appropriate indicators to be fed into the OptFor-EU decision support system to address the information needs and interests of the forest managers regarding improving the decarbonisation of forests through active forest management activities, especially in the face of global change.

We kindly ask you to rank the indicators in each category according to your information needs. Please put the most promising or interesting indicator on top.

The survey is conducted in English as there are no coherent translations of the indicators in other languages. However, in case of difficult comprehensibility we will assist you by email, on the phone or in a teleconference.

Time required to complete the questionnaire

Approximately 30 minutes.

Data privacy and confidentiality

All information provided (name, email, IP address) is kept confidential by encryption that turns all data into an unreadable format and only authorized persons from the project can decrypt the data and read it. Responses to the survey are confidential and will not be assigned to the interviewed stakeholder.

Online survey B for the national and international experts

Ranking of Essential Forest Mitigation Indicators

Project: OPTimising FOrEst management decisions for a low-carbon, climate resilient future in Europe (OptFor-EU)

Project duration

January 2023 -December 2026

Aim of the project

The primary objective of OptFor-EU, <https://optforeu.eu/> is to co-develop a user-centred Decision Support System (DSS) with forest managers and other forest stakeholders, that provides them with suitable climate adaptation and mitigation options for science-based optimising forest ecosystem services, including decarbonisation, and enhancing forest resilience and its capacities to mitigate climate change across Europe.

Objective of this survey

Involve experts on indicators for SFM and related data in the selection of indicators to be fed into an upscaled OptFor-EU decision support system to address information needs for eventual national to regional-level reporting regarding improving the decarbonisation of forests, especially in the face of global change.

We kindly ask you to rank the indicators in each category according to your information needs. Please put the most promising or interesting indicator on top.

The survey is conducted in English as there are no coherent translations of the indicators in other languages. However, in case of difficult comprehensibility we will assist you by email, on the phone or in a teleconference.

Time required to complete the questionnaire

Approximately 30 minutes.

Data privacy and confidentiality

All information provided (name, email, IP address) is kept confidential by encryption that turns all data into an unreadable format and only authorized persons from the project can decrypt the data and read it. Responses to the survey are confidential and will not be assigned to the interviewed stakeholder.

Note: The following online survey was identical for both groups of respondents

Survey

1) Please rank the following **forest area and primary production-related indicators** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonization:

Indicator	Rationale
Forest area by forest types (ha, %)	It is crucial to monitor changes in forest area to assess the effects of deforestation and the impact of forest restoration and afforestation efforts on carbon sequestration and other ecosystem services. Expanding the forest area enhances the potential for carbon mitigation by sequestering carbon in woody biomass and forest soils, depending on the forest types.
Forest area managed as continuous cover forestry of total forest area (ha, %)	Continuous cover management can enhance carbon sequestration by preventing soil erosion from cleared areas and enabling long-term carbon storage in trees of all age classes, thereby increasing the forest's carbon mitigation potential.
Forest expansion by afforestation (ha, %)	Forest expansion through afforestation (planting or seeding) of former non-forest areas, increases the carbon mitigation potential, as forests have the highest potential for carbon sequestration after wetlands.
Growing stock (m³/ha)	When a forest's growing stock increases, its capacity to store carbon in biomass also increases. As a result, the forest can help mitigate more carbon emissions. However, as the forest gets older and reaches its maximum carbon storage capacity, the rate of carbon sequestration may slow down.
Increment (m³/ha)	Increasing the increment increases the carbon sequestration in the living woody biomass, leading to a higher carbon mitigation potential of the forest.
Above-ground biomass stock (tons/ha)	Greater accumulation of biomass, both above- and below-ground, leads to increased carbon storage in the biomass, which contributes to carbon mitigation.
Wood removals in forest available for wood supply (m³/ha)	When trees are harvested for wood products, the amount of stored carbon in the forest is reduced. However, as long as the timber is not burned, the carbon remains stored in long-lived wood products contributing to carbon mitigation.

Comments:	
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2) Please rank the following **carbon storage-related indicators** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonization:

Indicator	Rationale
Carbon stored in forest biomass (tons/ha)	Increasing carbon stocks in forest biomass, both above- and below-ground, through sustainable forest management practices contributes to climate change mitigation.
Carbon stored in forest soils (tons/ha)	Reforestation and afforestation activities and different harvesting techniques impact soil carbon levels. For instance, reducing soil disturbance during logging operations, maintaining ground cover, and enhancing soil organic matter can help boost soil carbon sequestration.
Carbon stored in deadwood (tons/ha)	Increasing carbon storage in deadwood, whether standing or lying, is an important factor for climate change mitigation. In the early decomposition stages, deadwood serves as a carbon sink. Retention of deadwood during forest management operations thus contributes to climate change mitigation.
Carbon stored in harvested wood products (tons)	Carbon stored in long-lived harvested wood products, such as timber used in construction and furniture, also contribute to climate change mitigation as these products continue to sequester carbon throughout their lifespan.

Comments:	
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3) Please rank the following **forest health-related indicators** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonisation:

Indicator	Rationale
Degraded forest area (ha, %)	Degraded forests are those that have been damaged by illegal logging, fire, and any other abiotic or biotic damaging agents, leading to decreased levels of carbon sequestration and storage. This reduction in carbon storage capacity diminishes the forest's potential to mitigate carbon emissions, thus contributing to climate change.
Natural losses (Tree mortality) (m³/ha)	Natural losses through damaging agents, competition, water stress or senescence reduce the overall biomass available. This impacts the forest's capacity to absorb and store carbon.
Changes in tree cover density (%)	Negative changes in tree cover density caused by logging or by disturbances directly reduce the forest's carbon mitigation potential. As tree cover density decreases, the forest's stand resilience and capacity to sequester carbon diminishes.
Forest area damaged by severe weather events (storm, snow, ice, drought) (ha, %)	Severe weather events can cause significant damage to forests, resulting in large amounts of deadwood and carbon release into the atmosphere. Increased forest area damaged by such events decreases the carbon mitigation potential of living forest biomass and soils, thus contributing to climate change.
Forest area damaged by insects, diseases, wildlife, grazing (ha, %)	Damage caused by insects, diseases, wildlife, and grazing can lead to significant losses in forest biomass, reducing the forest's ability to sequester carbon. These disturbances can also disrupt the ecosystem balance, making forests more vulnerable to further, secondary damage.
Forest area damaged by fire (ha, %)	Forest fires result in huge amounts of deadwood and the immediate release of significant quantities of carbon into the atmosphere, thereby reducing the forest's capacity to store carbon. The expansion of forest areas affected by fire decreases the carbon mitigation potential of living forest biomass and soils, exacerbating climate change.
Salvage logging (removal of damaged or infected trees) (m³/ha)	When damaged, infected, and dead trees are removed through salvage logging, it can help store carbon in wood products and reduce the risk of carbon emissions from decomposing trees. However, the initial damaging event negatively impacts the overall carbon mitigation potential of a forest.
Soil condition (acidity, base saturation, supply of nutrients like calcium, magnesium, potassium, organic matter)	Healthy soil conditions in forests are crucial for productivity, water protection, and carbon sequestration. Proper soil management, including maintaining optimal acidity, nutrient levels, and organic matter, influences tree growth, species composition, and resilience to pests and diseases, thereby supporting decarbonisation efforts.
Forest restoration (damaged or degraded forest area restored) (ha, %)	Restoring degraded forests increases their potential for carbon sequestration and storage in both soil and woody biomass. Restoration also helps regain forest ecosystem services, such as biodiversity or water regulation. However, it's important to note that it may take several decades for a restored forest to reach the same level of carbon sequestration as before it was degraded. Post-damage restoration and preventative measures, such as controlled burns and firebreaks, are vital for minimizing fire damage and improving the resilience of the forest.

Comments:	
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4) Please rank the following **indicators related to climate change adaptability** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonisation:

Indicator	Rationale
Share of forest regeneration by natural regeneration (%)	Natural regeneration involves the renewal of a forest through the natural processes of seed dispersal, germination, and growth without human intervention. This can lead to the development of site-adapted species that are better suited to cope with climate change-induced changes such as drought and storms. Utilizing natural regeneration can enhance forest resilience, biodiversity, and carbon mitigation potential.
Share of natural regeneration not site-adapted (%)	Natural regeneration in stands with non-site-adapted trees may result in saplings and young trees not well-adapted to the specific site conditions. This can make the forest less resilient and reduce its carbon mitigation potential. Site-adapted species, whether they are native or non-native species, are better able to withstand climatic change-induced stresses.
Share of forest regeneration by planting and/or seeding of site-adapted species (%)	Actively planting or seeding site-adapted tree species involves human intervention to regenerate forests with native or non-native/introduced tree species chosen for their ability to thrive under current and anticipated climatic conditions. Increasing the share of regeneration through planting and seeding of more than one site-adapted tree species promotes a more structured, stable, and healthy forest enhancing the forest's carbon mitigation potential, resilience to disturbances, and biodiversity.

Comments:

5) Please rank the following **biodiversity-supporting indicators** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonisation:

Indicator	Rationale
Deadwood (standing/lying) (m³/ha)	An increase in deadwood, both standing and lying, increases the carbon stored in the forest stand, complementing the carbon stored in living biomass and forest soils. Deadwood is an important component of the carbon cycle by storing carbon until it decays.
Stand age (years/age classes, %)	As trees age, they sequester more carbon. Older stands store more carbon due to increased biomass accumulation, significantly contributing to the forest's overall carbon mitigation potential.
Multi-layer stands (ha, %)	Multi-layer stands, which have a diverse structure with trees of varying heights and ages, are highly effective in carbon sequestration. These stands accumulate more organic matter, capture solar radiation and carbon dioxide more efficiently, and retain carbon for longer periods. Their structural complexity enhances soil carbon storage and minimizes carbon loss during disturbances such as storms due to their higher resilience. Increasing the area of multi-layer stands can significantly enhance the forest's carbon mitigation potential.
Stand density (No of trees/ha)	The density of trees in a forest stand affects its carbon sequestration capacity. A higher density usually means greater carbon sequestration but there is an optimal range. Very dense stands may face competition for light, water, and nutrients. Thinning can optimize stand density, enhance growth, and improve resilience, thereby maximizing carbon storage.
Protected forest areas (ha, %)	Protected forest areas often have greater potential to mitigate carbon compared to forests managed for wood supply. This is because trees in protected areas can grow larger and live longer, enabling them to sequester more carbon over time. However, sustainably managed forests, with practices like selective harvesting and site-resilient reforestation, can sometimes sequester more carbon, especially when very old protected forests collapse.
Change in area of primary forest area (%)	Primary forests, undisturbed by human activities, generally have the highest carbon stocks, unless they are in the decay stage. Preserving primary forests is crucial for maintaining a high level of carbon sequestration.

Comments:

6) Please rank the following **stewardship-related indicators** according to their importance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonisation:

Indicator	Rationale
Forest area under an independently verified forest management certification system (ha, %)	Independently verified forest certification can be an effective tool for promoting sustainable forest management practices that enhance the forests' ability to sequester carbon and mitigate climate change. Increasing the certified forest area can have a positive impact on the forest's carbon mitigation potential by ensuring that certain management standards are followed.
Management intensity (increment/fellings, %)	Highly intensive management practices, such as high harvesting rates, can lead to reduced carbon sequestration potential and biodiversity loss, resulting in decarbonization losses. Sustainable harvesting practices aim to balance timber extraction with the maintenance of ecosystem integrity and carbon sequestration capacity.
Forest area under a long-term forest management plan (ha, %)	A long-term forest management plan focused on sustainable forest management practices can help maintain forest resilience in the face of climate change. This involves strategies to increase forest resilience and enhance the carbon mitigation potential of a forest.

Comments:	
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7) Please rank the following indicators which are important for **regional climate regulation** according to their relevance in your forest management practice towards enhancing forest decarbonization

Indicator	Rationale
Near-surface air temperature (°C)	Near-surface air temperature is influenced by forest management practices, geographical location, climate, soil, and vegetation. Temperature changes affect forest ecosystems, human health, and water availability. Forests help regulate temperature by influencing the fluxes of heat, momentum or water vapour. Forest management can help moderate local temperatures and contribute to regional climate regulation.
Precipitation (mm)	Forests influence regional precipitation patterns, including rain and snow, which can affect areas far from the forest. Changes in summer and winter precipitation can either positively or negatively impact a forest's decarbonisation rates, depending on the site resilience of the forest tree species. Managing forests to enhance their resilience to precipitation variability is crucial to maintaining their carbon mitigation potential and overall health.
Daily water vapour (relative humidity in %)	Forests affect near-surface water vapour by processes such as evapotranspiration and their structural characteristics, such as roughness length. These interactions with forest effects on wind and temperature influence local humidity levels and can affect phenomena such as fog formation. Near-surface humidity has significant implications for the comfort and health of humans, livestock, and wildlife, as well as the prevalence of plant diseases. Forest management practices that support and optimize water vapour fluxes can help regulate local climate and improve ecosystem health.
Leaf area index	The leaf area index (LAI) measures the amount of leaf surface area in relation to the ground area. It is a dimensionless value that indicates the density and extent of foliage in a forest canopy. A high LAI increases evapotranspiration, which cools the local climate by raising moisture fluxes. Conversely, a low LAI reduces evapotranspiration, resulting in warmer and drier conditions. LAI also affects albedo, impacting the surface energy balance and climate feedback mechanisms. Managing forests to maintain an optimal LAI can improve their ability to regulate climate.
Evapotranspiration (mm/m²)	Evapotranspiration, the process of water transfer from land to the atmosphere, is influenced by forest management practices. This process affects heat and moisture fluxes, near-surface humidity, temperature, and fog formation. In the upper atmosphere, it can influence cloud formation. Forest management that supports optimal evapotranspiration rates can help regulate local and regional climates.

Soil moisture (l water/m³ soil)	Forests have a significant impact on soil moisture levels due to their deep roots, transpiration rates, and ability to intercept rainfall. Soil moisture plays a crucial role in the local and regional water cycle and has a strong effect on tree health, water availability, and overall ecosystem resilience. It is essential to manage forests in a way that ensures adequate soil moisture levels, as this is key to supporting their carbon sequestration capabilities and ecological functions.
Runoff (mm)	Forests have a significant impact on runoff through their forest cover, forest types, soil structure, and interception capacity. Forest management practices that enhance a denser canopy cover and improve the soil structure can reduce runoff, improving water infiltration and storage in the soil. This has significant impacts on the local and regional water cycle, preventing soil erosion and maintaining water quality.

Comments:	
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